

CASE STUDY

Living archival practice and the choreographical navigations: Encounters and approaches with other-than-human persons

[version 1; peer review: 1 approved, 3 approved with reservations]

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Abstract

This article delves into the collaborative work of the interspecies dance collective, Mapped to the Closest Address (MaCA), focusing on our living archival practice and exploration of choreography with other-than-human persons. Through encounters with various species and environments, MaCA seeks to shift anthropocentric perspectives, interrogate their orientation towards modernity and coloniality, and question their understanding/administration/entanglement/devotion of, with, and to nature. The collective's journey, from a digital residency during the COVID-19 pandemic to site research, installations, and performance at the Echigo-Tsumari Art Triennale 2022, is documented and analyzed.

The collective's collaborative process involves relinquishing control to allow for the emergence of disobedient movements and the exploration of choreography from the perspective of other-than-human persons. This includes encounters with kudzu vines and mountains, weaving their movements and patterns into performances and installations. The article discusses the immersive performance "Turn Off the House Lights," in which MaCA integrates stories from local communities with gestures inspired by the landscape.

Through our living archival practice, MaCA aims to transmit a collective memory of interactions among organisms and environments and highlight the interconnectedness of humans and

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the other creatures of the Earth. The article reflects on the significance of choreography beyond human-centric notions, emphasizing the emergent forms of ecological performance and the dissolution of boundaries between human and non-human realms.

Drawing on interdisciplinary perspectives including dance, visual art, and theatre, MaCA's work exemplifies a cross-disciplinary approach to expressing the choreography of other-than-human persons. This approach not only presents audiences with immersive experiences but also responds to the future ecosystem through artistic exploration. Ultimately, MaCA's living archival practices contribute to awareness of the collective lives of other-than-human persons and offer insights into navigating our enmeshment with the natural world.

Keywords

Other-than-human persons, malfunction, disobedient movement, choreography

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Human beings are part of nature.

(Echigo-Tsumari Art Field, n.d.)

Introduction

From 2019 to 2022, Mapped to the Closest Address (MaCA) was an interspecies dance collective composed of four human animals (Colombian performance maker Alex Viteri Arturo, Colombian sound/light designer Catalina Fernandez, Japanese visual and performance artist Maharu Maeno, and Japanese dancer/choreographer Shuntaro Yoshida) and a cat, Violeta. Through choreographic practices, the humans in the group sought to interrogate their orientation towards modernity and coloniality, question their understanding/administration/entanglement/devotion of, with, and to nature, and shift their anthropocentric perspectives.¹ Collectively, we sowed practices to enter into contact with other-than-human persons. We used various devices to record our encounters and crafted multimedia social spaces to share our archive (Figure 1). The

Figure 1. Mushroom field surrounded by forest at El Arenero Yumita. 35mm black-and-white film. Photo by Alex Viteri Arturo.

¹ The concept of the Anthropocene highlights that the human-induced destruction of nature began in earnest as societies industrialized. The human-centered view of nature accompanying the term “Anthropocene” holds the key to retreating from modernity/globalization. As historian Dipesh Chakrabarti indicates, this encourages a historical dialogue with the human species living on the planet. However, when discussing the disrupted collective environment, it is essential to note that the terms “Anthropocene,” “human species,” and “nature” are tied to human agency. While the Anthropocene started in the industrial societies of the 19th century, environmental historian Jason W. Moore points out that the Age of Exploration in the pre-industrial 16th century was equally important. This is because the process through which natural resources are bought and sold cheaply is based on a system of Western colonialism. Humans view nature as a resource and render it into capital, creating an imbalance between humans and nature. Cultural critic and feminist Donna J. Haraway and geographer Kathryn Yusoff offer a different critique of the concept of the Anthropocene. In this academic category, we are applying diverse human and non-human players to consider on other-than-human persons’ performance. Thus, our standpoint has shifted from the notion of “the Anthropocene” and “more-than-human” associated with posthumanism to “Earth beings,” which approaches other species’ composition from a more symbiotic or altruistic perspective.

See: Chakrabarty, 2009, 212–220; Crutzen and Stoermer, 2013, 483–485; Haraway, 2016, 30–57; Moore, 2017, 620–621; Yusoff, 2018, 13–31

following discussions of our collaboration explore the history of our encounters.

This article considers our research-creation, from our recollections of a digital residency in 2020 during the COVID-19 pandemic to site research, installation, and performance at the Echigo-Tsumari Art Triennale 2022 in Niigata. We archived the movement of other species and collectively translated the awareness of local ecosystems within planetary and seasonal processes into our choreography.² In other words, through the accumulation of living archives, our collective memory of interactions among organisms and environment navigating the other-than-human persons’ choreography³ in the context of multispecies ethnography and animistic approaches in art creations. The detailed examination of these perspectives in “Turn Off the House Lights” aligned with emergent ecological performances. This sound-dance performance was held at the Echigo-Tsumari Art Triennale in 2022. Our creation process, involving other species, has focused on the interconnectedness of humans and non-humans. However, in this article, we turn our attention to the approaches to and significance of the choreography of other-than-human persons.

To explore our living archival practice, this article draws on dance and theatre writer Maša Radi Buh’s notion of ecological choreography, foregrounding not only the ecological experience of awareness but also the future ecosystem, imagining a post-apocalyptic time without humans through a geolocal sound walk that she mentioned. Furthermore, the choreography values “a (utopian) idea of a blurring of the distinction between (the value of) human and non-human creatures appears.”(Buh, 2022, 48) This article examines our ecological choreography strategies via malfunction and disobedient movement, revealing how such movements expose the dissolution of the border between human and non-human. Specifically, we aim to act out the transmission of our collective memory of landscape by encountering other-than-human persons. Our creation then shifts to tuning to local ecologies, and we encounter the notion of “disobedience” through other-than-human persons’ choreography. To illuminate the experience of heightened ecological awareness generated by disobedient movement, we speculate on the choreographic navigations.

² Artist Carolina Caycedo calls these “geo-choreographies.” This geo-choreography clarifies “how a seemingly mundane every gesture [...] can be given agency through language. The term geo-choreography is charged with political power that can be put to use when the river is threatened. The deeper the connection with the locality, the stronger the agency of the geo-choreography.” Here, the choreography means “the interactions of our bodies within that environment that hold knowledge, power and influence.” (Ostendorf-Rodriguez, 2023, 34–35)

³ Dance scholar and dramaturge Moritz Frischkorn speaks of “more-than-human choreography.” We speak of “other-than-human persons’ choreography” in the cross-cultural and trans-local perspectives aligning with the idea that the dance or movement practice is not solely a human activity but a collaborative and relational endeavor involving various elements of the environment, instead of using the word of post-human’s techno-romance and the more-than-human’s care practice for the attunement of more-than-human world. (Frischkorn, 2023, 19–21)

Malfunctioning video and non-human choreography: Open Forest Launch, a digital residency (Frankfurt an der Oder/Kōto-ku, Tokyo)

MaCA tended two vegetable gardens: a family's backyard garden in Hyogo (Maharu and Shuntaro) and a *Schrebergarten* in Frankfurt an der Oder (Catalina, Alex, and Violeta). We named the latter "Arenero Yumita" as a tribute to American scholar of Chicana feminism Gloria Anzaldúa and Catalina's mother Luz Marina Giraldo "Yumita." This represented a wishful naming for our queer family sanctuary and place to encounter and learn from other-than-human beings.⁴ Through MaCA's horticultural practice and research, we strived to cultivate a heightened awareness of planetary and seasonal processes and translated them into our notion of choreography.⁵

Unable to travel during the COVID-19 pandemic, we worked remotely, devising a digital residency to exchange the sensory

⁴ In the Lesbian Plenary Session, "Lesbian Alliances: Combating Heterosexism in the 80s," at the National Women's Studies Association 1988 Conference, philosopher Gloria Anzaldúa described four roles, or ways of being and of interacting in the world: bridge, drawbridge, sandbar, and island. "I sought and found the sandbar, a submerged or partly exposed ridge of sand built by waves offshore from a beach. To me, the sandbar feels like a more 'natural' bridge (though nature too, some argue, is a cultural construction) [...] For me the important thing is how we shift from bridge to drawbridge to sandbar to island. Being a sandbar means getting a breather from being a perpetual bridge without having to withdraw completely." (Anzaldúa, 2019, 147)

⁵ Our notion of choreography is about personal transformation, turning to disobedient beings, and relinquishing our mastery. Postcolonial scholar Julietta Singh states the following: "To survive mastery, we must begin to deconstruct our own movements (intellectual, activist, corporeal) that remain entangled with the violent erasures of other lives, and of things we declare insensate. Survival depends on new forms of living together, gathered in collectives that promise to astonish us." (Singh, 2018, 173–174)

experiences of our respective locations. Hosted by the Saison Foundation, we investigated various ways to relate with non-human beings.⁶ Our practices combined readings on non-human personhood with gardening. This led to "Open Forest Launch," a collection of videos documenting our exchanges uploaded to a digital world still in progress (Figure 2). (Mapped to the Closest Address, 2020a)

In the video diaries, we witness the slow growth of vegetables, join the Kiyosumi community garden in Tokyo (Figure 3 and Figure 4), and glimpse the depths of the Hellenesee, a sinking lake on the Germany-Poland border. (Mapped to the Closest Address, 2020b) We sought to draw attention to diverse human and non-human players to dislocate our anthropocentric standpoint and explore from other points of view the many worlds within gardens, forests, and lakes. A cat, Violeta joined the collective as a non-human videographer, and her material became a fundamental part of the work. She made several field trips with a miniature spy camera attached to her back. Violeta's footage served as one of the living archives that revealed and documented how she moved. Similarly, we reimagined her life and world through her actions, such as following her gaze and climbing up trees, and communicating with crows along with Violeta (Figure 5). In her video, we noticed the impossibility of translating concepts between the humans and the non-humans, so we decided to cohabit with non-human movement.

The camera captured a view from a much lower position than a human's camera would be placed and produced seemingly chaotic images. We were exploring with the camera,

⁶ MaCA was funded by The Saison Foundation's "Saison AIR Partnership" from 2020 to 2022.

Figure 2. Screenshot of "Open Forest Launch" in progress. Photo by Catalina Fernandez.

Figure 3. Kiyosumi community garden in Kōtō-ku. Photo by Shuntaro Yoshida.

Figure 5. Scene from “Open Forest Launch_Video Diaries.” Captured by Violeta and edited by Catalina Fernandez.

Kudzu and mountains as other-than-human personhood: Clumsy-seeming mountains and site research (Tokamachi)

MaCA received a second invitation, this time to participate in the Echigo-Tsumari Art Triennale (ETAT).⁷ We traveled several times to the province, visited our assigned space, and planned for field research. The city of Tokamachi is surrounded by mountains, which are called *satoyama*.⁸ Prior to the opening of the festival, Shuntaro, Maharu, and architect Jun Yamaguchi⁹ stayed at Yamaneko Guest House to explore the three nearby mountains: Akiba, Gongen, and Takaba. They encountered and collected kudzu vines from up in the hills around the guest house (Figure 6). While craftsmen of the ancient Jōmon periods (c. 14000 to 300 BCE) utilized kudzu for fibers and cloth, few such techniques remain. Today, the vine is deemed invasive and categorized as a weed. However, after engaging in processes like boiling, fermenting (Figure 7), and river-washing to gauge its durability, we shifted our perspective on kudzu. We recognized our intricate connection with kudzu and choreographed movements reflecting this entanglement. We learned from kudzu’s weaving patterns, integrating them into our mountain portraits for the installation. We followed the patterns as if dancing, by handweaving the dried leaves. The choreographic score comprised, in Jun’s words, “covering,” “spreading in search of the sun,” and “intertwining.” These extended non-human choreographies were knitted again how

Figure 4. Scene from “Open Forest Launch_Video Diaries.” Captured by Violeta and edited by Catalina Fernandez.

which was bound by her pace and the fact that she was on four legs. Accepting the malfunction of the video was also a way of relinquishing mastery over the final art product. As the camera had been given to Violeta, human choreography committed to her and there was no way we could control her moves: where she went, how long she decided to stay in a spot, and how fast she was. We relinquished the mastery over the video capture to Violeta. The video diary, including her perspectives, was also an attempt to take our thinking past human phenomena to a place beyond the human. Thus, the footage served as a portal that allowed us to escape, although briefly, from our human perspective.

⁷ “The Echigo-Tsumari Art Triennale (ETAT) is one of the largest art festivals in the world as well as the pioneer of regional art festivals now taking place across Japan. It has provided an alternative way to explore *satoyama* following artworks as guiding lights, which has received great attention both within and outside Japan as a leading practice of community building through art.” (Echigo-Tsumari Art Field, 2023)

⁸ *Satoyama* originally denoted any mountains in rural Japanese villages before gaining more specific ecological significance. Initially exploited by forestry and mining industries since the 1950s, many *satoyama* regions faced devastation and abandonment by the 1970s. This led to a movement advocating for nature’s safeguarding. The momentum swelled in the 1990s with heightened global environmental awareness. Japan’s Ministry of the Environment incorporated *satoyama* protection into its ecological planning during the same period. See: Okada, 2017, 65–66

⁹ For Echigo-Tsumari Art Triennale 2022, MaCA was joined by architect Jun Yamaguchi.

Figure 6. Maharu Maeno and Jun Yamaguchi cutting kudzu. Photo by Shuntaro Yoshida.

Figure 7. Kudzu fermentation (Pictured: J. Yamaguchi and M. Maeno). Photo by Shuntaro Yoshida.

plants live and move on the land, and we noticed their life compositions.¹⁰ We stayed close to kudzu in terms of our embodied knowledge as inheritors of their movements.

¹⁰ When we think of non-human's expanded choreography in the history of choreography, we can situate the choreographic object as non-human. For instance, dance historian and dramaturgist Anna Leon comments on a choreographed tree in choreographer William Forsyth's Groningen Project. She observes that "people control nature, and choreographers define the movement of bodies – in an expansion of choreography, the choreographer controls nature and defines the forms that it will embody." (Leon, 2022, 191)

However, we theorize an other-than-human choreography that relativizes the non-human's non-danceable movement and more-than-human's non-moving movement. based on Western notions. A key point is the cross-cultural approach that avoids a singular Western notion and offers the clumsy-seemingness which deconstructs a central point of view and proposes more symbiotic and altruistic worldviews and approaches.

While contemplating the mode of existence of kudzu and the functional workings of these life forms, we explored the choreography of the intelligence of plants through the practice of listening to their rhythms and movements. Their tips were growing very vigorously in the summer. Listening to and cohabiting with their movements, we unravel the composition of kudzu. Becoming attentive to kudzu also leads to an acceptance of the mountains, the "Earth beings" which allow us to engage in a sensory dialogue with organic matter. (de la Cadena, 2015, 105)¹¹

While researching the Akiba 秋葉, Gongen 権現, and Takaba 高場 mountains, which surround the exhibition site, we encountered multispecies stories. At the summit of Akiba mountain stands a shrine dedicated to Akiha Sanjakubo 秋葉三尺坊 or Akiha Gongen 秋葉権現, which is a manifestation of the Buddha as a Shinto god of fire protection appearing as a long-nosed Japanese goblin called a *tengu* 天狗 (a divine being in Japanese folklore). During the Edo period (1603–1867), Akiha Sanjakubo was widely revered as having control over fire. Akihabara 秋葉原, the neighborhood of Tokyo where we bought electric parts for our installation, is renowned globally for anime and subculture, and derives its name from the Akiha Gongen. Legend has it that the technique for extracting thread from kudzu was developed by a Shugendo practitioner in Kakegawa, Shizuoka prefecture, not far from another Akiha mountain. (Fukatsu, 2008, 41) To this day, kudzu cloth continues to be crafted in Kakegawa. The mountains transmitted knowledge to us, and we were tuning in to their rhythms rather than the other way around.

Through kudzu movements and our gestures (boiling, fermenting, and river-washing) which render kudzu into fiber, we encountered a composition of kudzu which tells of the loss of craft skills in an era of modernization (Figure 8 and Figure 9). When we translate the kudzu movement into dance scores, the witness of kudzu links the memory of local territories and the presence of *satoyama*. *Satoyama* attunes us to the rhythm of kudzu in Echigo's ecosystem and debates the symbiosis between humans and non-humans. However, we do not only demonstrate that "human beings are part of nature," but also that kudzu and Akiba mountain in their other-than-human personhood echo with the past and future of the life cycle and resist human control – we watch the clumsy-seeming mountains.

Navigation of the living archives and ecological considerations: *Clumsy-Seeming Mountains*, the installation (Tokamachi Snow Center)

Our installation was housed in the Risetsu Shinsetsu Sougou Center, Tokamachi Snow Center (our translation), a former bathhouse surrounded by rice fields. In the winter, the two-floor

¹¹ Anthropologist Marisol de la Cadena reflects on issues of paramount concern to current anthropology, from the meanings of indigeneity in the context of multiculturalism to the contested agency of nonhumans and material things. She says, "I do not translate earth-beings as spirits or gods, nor am I saying that the peasant struggle for land was motivated by nonsecular, or religious, modes of conscience" (de la Cadena 2015, 105).

Figure 8. Washing kudzu (Pictured: J. Yamaguchi and M. Maeno). Photo by Shuntaro Yoshida.

Figure 10. Tokamachi Snow Center in Winter 2020. Photo by Maharu Maeno.

Figure 9. Kudzu fiber. Photo by Shuntaro Yoshida.

Figure 11. Tokamachi Snow Center in Winter 2020. Photo by Maharu Maeno. Figure 11 has been reproduced with permission from participant A, B, C, D, E F and G. Edits were made for de-identification purposes with permission from Maharu Maeno.

building serves as an emergency shelter and a croquet ground (Figure 10 and Figure 11). Our multimedia archive stood on the field's artificial grass.

The installation emulated a sci-fi bathhouse. We installed red filters in the overhead lamps and windows and played a sci-fi soundtrack composed by Catalina using sounds from natural environments and electronic noise (Figure 12). The whole experience made the cricket field seem slightly “off” to

Figure 12. Threading kudzu vines (Pictured: J. Yamaguchi). At his back is the scaled-down version of El Arenero Yumita. Photo by Catalina Fernandez.

locals and visitors. The deep red of the interior gave the greens a particular intensity, a visual illusion similar to the water stage in Min Tanaka's Butō performance, highlighting the presence of rice fields around our installation.¹² In the field, we placed TVs with our video diaries, documentation of the vine's entanglements, three-dimensional kudzu-threaded mountains, dance scores, poems, and a model of El Arenero Yumita's house. Outside, we installed a scaled-down version of Yamaneko's Guest House and a double print of Frederic Church's portrait of Mount Cotopaxi (Figure 13).¹³ Visitors were invited to explore the grounds barefoot, encounter the trembling mountains, and have a glimpse of our video and photo archives (Figure 14).

By placing MaCA's archives, we aimed to link the collective's past to the rice fields and the mountains, a living archive just outside of the exhibition space. However, the presence of rice fields slowly transforms outside and humans harvest rice according to the seasonal cycle. Rice fields represent the time-space between nature as wild and as tame. The performance

Figure 13. Outside, the scaled-down version of Yamaneko Guest House with a portrait of Mt. Fuji and a double reproduction of Frederic Church's portrait of Mount Cotopaxi. Photo by Julie Lee. Figure 13 has been reproduced with permission from Julie Lee.

¹² We witnessed Min Tanaka's performance during our visit to Echigo-Tsumari Art Triennale 2022. The museum was packed with locals and visitors who had all come to see the renowned Butō dancer. Tanaka performed in the museum's open courtyard, filled with water. A delicate mist veiled the stage, enhancing the illusion of a natural setting. Against the backdrop of the museum's concrete walls, through the dense fog, we watched his silhouette and the subtle articulations of his limbs. Sometimes he vanished, enveloped by the watery matter, only to resurface as if emerging from a bomb attack. Both Tanaka and the fog moved according to a finely crafted dramaturgy. His body was seamlessly integrated with the theatrical machine, continuing the orchestrated illusion of naturalness within the museum's confines. The performative device skillfully enacted naturalness and created an impression of nature's defiance, which Shuntaro calls disobedience. Still, we remained mindful of its controlled precision.

¹³ Although Church's 19th-century painting depicts nature, it does so as a spectacle to be admired rather than inhabited. The pine tree in Church's painting, for instance, could not exist in a real landscape. Church fictionalized nature in his portrayal of naturalness. (Kusserow, 2018, 117–25)

Figure 14. Detail of our installation *Clumsy-Seeming Mountains* in 2022. Photo by Catalina Fernandez. Figure 14 has been reproduced with permission from participant H. Edits were made for de-identification purposes with permission from Catalina Fernandez.

of rice fields enmeshes people in plant agencies. Even though rice fields have been heavily domesticated, they continue to exhibit behaviors that are not solely driven by human desires; rather, they also demonstrate their own performances. Indeed, visitors are aware of the performance of rice fields and watch three huge mountain objects, each about three to five meters in diameter, made by collecting and weaving local kudzu, hung in the space. Mountains made of kudzu in the building and the real mountains outside guided the visitors to in-between perspectives. Mountains were vessels of organisms and living archives in order that visitors walked around inside/outside of mountains, staying close to Earth beings. Thus, the choreography of the clumsy-seeming mountains reopens the discussion of ecological considerations and brings a sense of kinship.

Surprisingly, we struggled to find second-hand, recycled materials for the installation. The vast amount of e-waste produced in Japan is a serious concern for the Japanese environmental movement,¹⁴ and the use of second-hand materials does not seem to be a common practice. We searched for used headphones, cables, and transmitters in the basement of a second-hand, recycled materials store in Akihabara, Tokyo. As plastic packaging has become an omnipresent part of our daily existence in Japan, we found it challenging to adhere to eco-friendly practices (Figure 15).

An emergent form of ecological performance: "Turn Off the House Lights," an immersive performance

During our time at Echigo-Tsumari Art Triennale 2022, we listened to rice farmers, local volunteers, and sightseers. For

¹⁴ Several laws were introduced by the Japanese government to promote e-waste recycling and effective utilization of resources. At present, Japan is widely considered to have the best functioning e-waste management system in terms of citizen compliance levels and the amount of e-waste recovered. See Izzat Rasnan, Fariz Mohamed, Ta Goh, and Watanabe 2016, 1–23

our contribution to the exhibition, we shared MaCA's atmospheric performance "Turn Off the House Lights," adapting the script to the region's stories and integrating movements and gestures inspired by our interactions with the landscape and the people. "Turn Off the House Lights" transformed our embodied research into a tangible experience, immersing our guests in the sensuous realms of real, imagined, and imaginations-of-real landscapes (Figure 16). (Tamler, 2022)

In the Berlin rendition of "Turn Off the House Lights," we guided guests wearing wireless headphones from a dance studio to a horticultural garden, stewarding them through an imagined forest (Figure 17). The outside community garden features several islands of flowers and plants cared for by neighbors. Together, we meandered – something like taking a walk while chatting on the phone with a loved one or sitting with a group of friends to listen to a thunderstorm. We convened around a bonfire to witness the sunset. Our narrations layered Tokyo's

Figure 15. Collecting materials at Eco Factory in Muikamachi, 2022 (Pictured: A. Viteri Arturo). Photo by Catalina Fernandez.

Figure 16. Rice field dance, "Turn Off the House Lights," 2022 (Pictured: S. Yoshida). Photo by Catalina Fernandez.

Figure 17. Instagram post, "Turn Off the House Lights" at Cordillera Berlin, 2022 (Pictured: S. Yoshida and A. Viteri Arturo). Photo by Maharu Maeno.

urban views with Frederic Church's portrayal of the Andean mountain chain.¹⁵ Our script aimed to challenge colonial interpretations of the landscape and delved into the mountains' spiritual lives. (de la Cadena 2015, 25)

Conversely, the Japanese version incorporated embodied renditions of our visits to Takaba mountain, gestures developed while handling kudzu, and stories from local rice field farmers. We wanted visitors to have an immersive experience that reflected the experience of viewing Mt. Fuji while submerged in a hot spring, part of Japan's bathhouse culture. While Maharu and Alex told stories, Catalina mixed our soundscape live, Jun sewed kudzu fibers, and Shuntaro performed non-human choreographies – he became a spider in a bathhouse, a bird in a rice field, the pine tree in Church's paintings, a cherry tree beside the river in Kotō-ku, a kudzu vine, and one stalk among the many in the rice fields. Emerging from the back of the rice fields and returning to them towards the end, he describes the experience as the following of disobedient movements, something in between the wildness of the mountains and the domesticated nature of the fields (Figure 18):

I tried to draw every movement from the environment. I moved in response to the wind, the clouds, the weaving of the rice fields, followed mountain ridges, and channeled distant rainfalls. The more I was invested in their movement, the lighter my movements became. In the in-betweenness of domestic and wild, the body's senses did not know which nature it was responding to.¹⁶

In the performance of "Turn Off the House Lights," the rhythms of the body and nature resonate through the sensory and perceptual (re)organization induced by other-than-human persons' choreography. Dance scholar Tamara Ashley's proposal for ecological choreography introduces and expands

¹⁵ We used the painting of *Cotopaxi* (1855) by Frederic Edwin Church.

¹⁶ Shuntaro Yoshida, discussion with Alex Viteri Arturo, July 21, 2023.

Figure 18. Cherry tree beside the river in “Turn Off the House Lights,” 2022 (Pictured: S. Yoshida). Photo by Osamu Nakamura. Figure 18 has been reproduced with permission from Osamu Nakamura.

upon the notion of performances that are primarily linked to place. (Ashley, 2012, 27) Going against this, dance and theatre writer Maša Radi Buh explains that the location is sequentially changed and updated in trans-geolocation choreography through the sound walk. She mentions the updated ecological choreography in the following:

Ecological choreography not only incites an ecological experience of awareness through theatrical content but offers an experience through the medium itself as well. The difference between the former and the latter is that one of them counts on the audience’s feelings while the other engages them with embodied ways of attending and perceiving.

(Buh, 2022, 47)

Maša proposes a geolocational multimedia soundwalk as ecological choreography. Such a performance engages the attendee through a physical attunement which is connected to two interpretations of listening, both connected to artistic practices aiming to aid the body in experiencing some type of ecological awareness. Participants listen to a set of audio tracks which correspond to certain locations along the route, with interconnected elements giving the sense of a unified event. She describes the connection between the three elements of space, time and sound, and the connection “exemplifies the principle of interconnectedness taken over from ecology as the change or fault in the execution of one of them significantly alters the performance itself, as well as the participant’s experience.” (Buh, 2022, 47–48) Maša’s ecological experience of awareness indicates attentive walking and recalls the absence of the noises of civilization during the COVID-19 pandemic. In our performance in Berlin, we challenged the soundwalk, inviting gardens into an embodied practice. However, simply told, our performance at Echigo-Tsumari Art Triennale 2022 couldn’t avoid theatrical frameworks such as the division of space between stage and auditorium

space because we couldn’t use remote headphones in Japan.¹⁷ During the performance in Echigo-Tsumari, guests were located between live narrators (behind guests) and performer, and the fixed location prevented the changes and contingencies of participants moving the environmental structure.

Conclusion

This essay has presented our collective research-creation and “Turn Off the House Lights,” a work of other-than-human choreography. The choreography navigated the border zone between human and non-human, which emphasized ecology territories inciting an ecological experience of awareness. Our ecological performance is not only a constant opening of new imaginative spaces by surrendering and reacting to the (in)visible and disordered gestures and irregular movements of living and inanimate living objects, but also a narrative choreographic practice that is intertwined with the global environment in each place and with each time. During site research, we were looking for entanglements, tuning to the territory’s ecologies. We actualized the script with the voices and atmosphere of each place, responding to our host environment. Therefore, in these living archival practices, the other-than-human persons’ choreography is effectively expressed in cross-disciplinary ways – visual art, music, lighting, dance, theatre, and text – while at the same time finding clues to respond to the future ecosystem through the back-and-forth of the incommensurable noises of the malfunction and disobedience of which Earth’s beings are composed.

Writer, translator, and interdisciplinary artist Cory Tamler interviewed us at Morishita Studio after the performance of “Turn Off the House Lights” at the Echigo-Tsumari Triennale (Figure 19). She wrote about our work:

[The] research and creation process is one of shared archiving, a kind of living accumulation – analogous, in my mind, to the simultaneous growth and decomposition in a garden. The collective (de)composes their archive through the exchange of gardening techniques and a “practice of encounter” (in their words) with non-humans, but also through their varied artistic practices, from sound and visual art to dance.

(Tamler, 2022)

Our living archival practices are comprised of the transmission and performance of other-than-human persons’ lives and forms.

From digital residency and site research to installation and performance, our living archives accumulate, on the one hand, the conceptual malfunction that spills over from material exploration. The malfunctions that appear during the creative

¹⁷ In Berlin, we could use long-distance remote headphones for the silent disco club. In Japan, however, we could not use them for performances because most products are made overseas and do not comply with the technical standards of the Japanese Radio Law; such headphones were very expensive, even to rent.

Figure 19. “*広い島/HIROSHIMA NO TIENE NADA QUE ENVIDIARLE A PARIS,*” hosted by The Saison Foundation, Tokyo, 2022 (Picured M. Maeno and C. Fernandez). Photo by Taro Inamura. Figure 19 has been reproduced with permission from Taro Inamura. Edits were made for de-identification purposes with permission from Taro Inamura.

process address phenomena beyond the human and open the way for an escape from the anthropocentric perspective. On the other hand, a feeling of substantive disobedience spills over from transcendental exploration. The disobedient movement of other species dissolves the dichotomy of human and non-human, and changes to the tuning of their rhythm in an intentional break from the dramaturgical framework. Our senses shifted back and forth in the encounters with other-than-human persons' choreography, underlining the way other-than-human approaches reflect the complex relationship between humankind and the natural world. However, living archival practice in a collective life can contribute to concern

and care for both the Earth and the disobedient movement of its living beings. This practice helps sustain the collective lives of other-than-human persons and their ecosystems.

At the time of writing, our artistic practice only incites the awareness of environmental awareness. Furthermore, considering the Earth's rapid deterioration over a decade, it is significant that we consider how artistic works represent ecological choreography. Despite the development of theories of the Anthropocene and posthumanism, these have primarily been applied to science and artwork rather than interdisciplinary research. Thus, we argue for a more radical development of embodied practices and interactions between human and non-human environments to elicit a new investigation of the relationship between the human and the non-human that may be experienced by audiences. Most importantly, cross-disciplinary perspectives should transform collaboration in the collective through encounters with other-than-human persons, opening the way to further living archival practices.

Ethics and consent

Ethical approval and consent were not required. The authors confirm that consent to publish the name of Luz Marina Giraldo. Any identifiable information has been used with explicit permission for publication. Regarding the consent to publish identifiable details, written informed consent was obtained via her family member because she has passed away.

Data availability

No data are associated with this article.

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Version 1

Reviewer Report 20 November 2024

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Natalie Schiller

The University of Auckland, Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand

Reading this article might urge the reader to get down on their hands and knees to re-experience the world from an *other-than-human* perspective (at least this is what happened to me!). In this case study, the authors celebrate the propositions of *other-than-human* choreographies and ecological choreographies. The authors are part of the international and interspecies collective *Mapped to the Closest Address (MaCA)* and cartograph four events of their research-creation in this writing. Here, they introduce their insights from their digital residency (*Open Forest Launch*), site-research, installation (*Clumsy-Seeming Mountains*), and immersive performance (*Turn Off the House Lights*). Their work intra-mingles *earth beings*, such as a cat, kudzu vines, and mountains (*satoyama*), and *other-than-human* performative actions, such as processes of fermenting. *Other-than-human* entanglements stimulate ideas on *disobedient* and *malfunctioning* movements. The choreographies seem to emerge in “zone[s] of indiscernibility” (Massumi, 2014, p. 8), where notions of the “domestic” and the “wild” (article p. 9) are con-fused.

This case study is well written and allows the reader to encounter a *tacit* and *felt* knowledge that research-creation seeks to offer (Loveless, 2019; Nelson, 2022). This writing is a unique and significant contribution to the realm of research-creation and captures essences of the concepts on how and when assemblages of *other-than-human* beings and ecological choreographies can activate artistic practices.

With a focus on *other-than-human beings*, I encourage the authors to re-evaluate the chosen words and if those terminologies mirror the dynamics of their research-creation they seek to express with this case study. For example, the term “other-than-human persons” has mainly been applied throughout the case study, although on page 10 the word person has been left out, creating “other-than-human choreography”, which for me captures the particularities and core of this research-creation more specifically.

Furthermore, could the integration of *intra* (Barad, 2007) emphasise notably the ethos and dynamics of the *more-than-human* configurations within the case study? Barad’s agential realism thrives on its neologism of *intra*, where *intra* “signifies the mutual constitution of entangled agencies

...[and] agencies are only distinct in relation to their mutual entanglement; they don't exist as individual elements" (p. 33). Therefore, the authors could consider implementing instead of *inter* or *cross* an *intra*. For example, interconnectedness (p. 2, 3, & 10) could morph into intra-connectedness, interactions (p. 2, 3, 9, & 11) could transform into intra-actions, and cross-disciplinary (p. 11) could be intra-disciplinary.

On another note, the work of Katja Aglert et al. (2024) might be of interest to the authors.

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Is the background of the case's history and progression described in sufficient detail?

Yes

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full access and reuse by other researchers?

No source data required

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the data and analysis?

Yes

Is the case presented with sufficient detail to be useful for teaching or other practitioners?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: My areas of expertise lie within artistic research, feminism, performance arts, performance philosophy, and posthuman/new materialism theories. My projects seek to explore how artistic research supports critical, creative, and affirmative approaches of becoming and being in a contemporary world. Some of my work has been published via the following articles: (2020) 'Experiments in Motion – An entanglement of dancing hips and domesticity.' *RIACT – Journal of Artistic Research, Creation and Technology*, 1(1), 51-75, (<https://researchspace.auckland.ac.nz/handle/2292/54430>) and (2017) 'Breathe through your vagina! — An attempt to catch ineffability.' *Dance Research Aotearoa*, 5(1), 47-58 (<https://doi.org/10.15663/dra.v5i1.60>). I am a member of the international posthuman reading and

writing group, Posthumanism in/as Artistic Practices, and associate editor with The International Journal of Education and the Arts.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard.

Reviewer Report 19 November 2024

<https://doi.org/10.21956/openreseurope.18854.r45661>

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Stefanie Gabriele Sachsenmaier

Middlesex University London, London, England, UK

The article documents the artistic practice of the dance collective Mapped to the Closest Address, outlining a series of its projects since 2020. It discusses the collective's creative processes and methods, thematising issues such as human and other-than-human relations, disobedient movements, interconnectedness between human and more/other-than-humans, entanglement, ecological awareness etc.

The strength of the article is its perspective of the makers who provide insights into the creative processes and critical approaches explored. It includes a strong resource of visual materials, which convey the artistic practices in a mixed mode to the reader.

What might be further considered in developing the work is its rather long list of keywords, partially listed above. While these are very current terms and there is a sense of how these belong together, as such these concepts remain largely undefined and under-explored. Indicatively, questions open up along the lines of what constitute practices of disobedience and in what ways the documented practice might align and perhaps also expand these.

Furthermore, the article comprises a long list of footnotes, which, if to be read in line with the main text, create a disruption to the flow of reading. While some of these materials do indeed work well in footnote form, others provide details that seem key to understanding the thinking that is developed in the main text. It would be helpful if the authors considered to place some of the materials presented in footnotes into the main body of the writing, where the respective ideas further outlined seem vital to the understanding of the discussion.

I would also point to an opportunity for further criticality of the collective's practice in view of considering its practice in view of ecological practices, such as for instance critically commenting on the carbon footprint it incurs. A slightly more self-critical view would also help to frame the writing as a mode of ongoing enquiry into the rich, and crucially challenging, ideas and concepts presented, rather than presenting these as having been achieved in their artistic practices.

Is the background of the case's history and progression described in sufficient detail?

Yes

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full access and reuse by other researchers?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the data and analysis?

Yes

Is the case presented with sufficient detail to be useful for teaching or other practitioners?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Performance practice, performance processes, process philosophy, posthumanism, performance and politics

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Reviewer Report 12 November 2024

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Ian Garrett

York University, Toronto, Ontario, Canada

The article by Yoshida et al. explores the interspecies dance collective, Mapped to the Closest Address (MaCA), and their approach to choreography with other-than-human persons. It details their living archival practices from a digital residency during the COVID-19 pandemic to performance installations at the Echigo-Tsumari Art Triennale 2022. The collective incorporates non-human elements like a feline collaborator, kudzu vines and mountains into their work, aiming to break down human-centric views and foster an ecological awareness through emergent and disobedient choreography.

The article presents an innovative and compelling approach to ecological and environmental site-specific choreography, emphasizing interactions between humans and non-human entities. It successfully introduces concepts like “malfunction” and “disobedient movement,” which challenge traditional human-centered choreography practices. The analysis of MaCA’s performances and installations provides a rich narrative, drawing attention to the interconnectedness of human and non-human-collaborators.

There are areas where the clarity and organization of the paper could be improved:

Terms such as “malfunction,” “disobedient movement,” and “other-than-human persons” need clearer initial definitions, at least to understand the use by the authors. While they’re well considered and appropriate, the unfamiliar reader would benefit for help in understanding how these are being used more explicitly. Introducing these concepts earlier with brief definitions on what is meant by their use in the paper would help readers understand the framework without having to refer to later sections or accept ambiguity with their own understanding.

I think it would be useful to also unpack the focus on the idea of the “non-human person”. While collaboration with non-human entities or non-human collaborators has become relatively common in at least some conversations, there use of “person” is an interesting divergence and may load the reader’s understanding with a specific idea of the relationship between humans and non-humans as people, which feels like it can pull the efforts of the authors to explore the non-anthropocentric views of their non-humans by suggesting their personhood and the social relationships and rights of personhood in anthropocentric frameworks. For this reviewer, it pulled the understanding of the relationship to each of the non-human collaborators towards the anthropocentric and may undermine the idea. Further to this, it also feels like the authors would benefit from the addition of writing on their thinking about the ability of humans and non-humans to share experiences given the differences in physiology, neurology, and each’s distinct evolved sensorium.

There are allusions to this consideration, such as the citation of Frickhorn on pg. 3. I think this is particularly important in the description of Shutaro’s expression of non-human choreographies on pg. 9, where I’m curious to hear about the introduction of human reasoning and creative decision making in translating the non-human to the human and what sort of fidelity is possible and what further mutual understanding is found in recognizing these uncrossable boundaries between human and non-human experiences of the world.

As an important distinction stemming from this thinking, when it comes to the Ethics and Consent section at the end, It would be helpful to confirm that the fact that Ethics approval was not required was confirmed by an IRB. Given the choice to refer to collaborators as “non-human persons” there is a question of the anthropocentric concept of ethics and consent in a research context. If the non-human collaborators are being given personhood, then it stands to reason that there would need to be consider of the risks and potential harms to the non-humans and associated ethical approaches. This reinforces the need to be explicit and intentional about the use of this term. So, while an IRB may not require further consent and indicates it does not require further approval based on institutional risk, what are the ethics of the researchers if non-humans are positioned as persons?

The article would also benefit from restructuring certain paragraphs to improve coherence. For

example, the section discussing kudzu vines and mountains could be presented in a way that better integrates the description of site-specific practices with the underlying theoretical concepts.

It may also be useful to add an early paragraph with a clear timeline of activities along with their locations, and how other locations are layered. For example, on pg. 9, there is reference to the Berlin iteration of the work, which was a location less clear to me as a site of performance early. This discussion the layering of Tokyo over the experience, and I was unclear about how these geospatial relationships were being described. The following paragraph then describes the Japanese version, which presents some confusion given the scale of the location and the previous description of a specific city in Japan being layered over an experience in Berlin. This may also be useful as chart/matrix as an additional figure or appendix to provide the reader with a clear understanding of how the authors layered locations and to offer easy reference to the spatial context of each iteration.

Overall, the concepts are expressed well. It may be worth addressing dangling modifiers and eliminating colloquial expressions which would make the text more polished. Please also use surnames consistently. There are many specific and excellent suggestions by the previous review which I will suggest the authors heed instead of listing them again.

It would primarily benefit from providing greater clarity for the unfamiliar reader, so that specific terms and the temporal and spatial planning of the performance work is clear so that the focus is on the author's critical understanding of their findings, which are somewhere clouded by these ambiguities. Most importantly, a clear understanding, and consistency in the language used to refer to non-human components and either some additional writing on why the authors have positioned non-humans in this way and/or acknowledgements of the limits of human understanding of non-human perspectives would be beneficial to reinforce the de-anthropocentric goals of the paper and the work it described.

I would suggest that the authors may consider Una Chaudhuri's *The Stage Lives of Animals* to develop a deeper critical approach to the complexities of non-human expression in performance.

Is the background of the case's history and progression described in sufficient detail?

Partly

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full access and reuse by other researchers?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the data and analysis?

Partly

Is the case presented with sufficient detail to be useful for teaching or other practitioners?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Extensive research/creation experience focused on ecological design for performance or "ecoscenographic" approaches to performance and time-based art publishing across Theatre, Dance, and Performance Studies and Digital Environmental Humanities with a focus on extended reality technologies in site-specific and geolocated performance projects and the ethics of this work, in part through non-human collaboration working both as an international touring artist, and through a variety of peer-reviewed publications. Educator focused on ecoscenography, devised and site-specific performance and research creation supervising graduate students on related project as former director of graduate program of Theatre, Dance, and Performance studies.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.

Reviewer Report 08 October 2024

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Teresa Heiland

University Of North Carolina, Greensboro, North Carolina, USA

Answers to questions:

1. Is the background of the case's history and progression described in sufficient detail?

The study's background history and progression are mostly clear. I did find one paragraph on page 7 that, if brought far earlier in the paper, would improve reader's comprehension of the work. I have noted it below. I have also gathered a list of many syntactical and word-choice needs in the writing that could be improved to ensure reader understanding.

1. Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

The work references the theme and progression of the activities. The well-known literature of Anna Halprin and Lawrence Halprin might be of interest to this group. Anna Halprin's work was about relating to nature. Her husband Lawrence Halprin created gardens for visitors or dances. They both also wrote scores and related to nature in ways that spiritually parallel your work. Lawrence Halprin's RSVP cycles, page 3 might be a place to start reading. Their work might inspire these authors. Literature seems sufficient, although some of it comes far later in the paper than what is traditionally done. This choice of adding literature later than the way most academic papers read causes the flow to feel less focused and directed than it could.

1. If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate? NA

2. Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility? To have full reproducibility, a list of items used in each of your projects might be helpful. Would a map of the locations be useful as well? For example, how far into natural areas did you travel? People unfamiliar with Japan might not be able to picture the locations without reference points. We will have to Google the locations ourselves. I'm not implying these lists and maps are needed but I think in
3. Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results? Yes.
4. Is the case presented with sufficient detail to be useful for teaching or other practitioners? Some concepts need to be fleshed out more. See my notes below. Also, the word posthumanism is mentioned in footnote 1, but not in the text until the last page (page 11). I would double check to make sure you have fleshed out all the key terms early to introduce the philosophies and concepts early.

Approved with reservations:

The article needs some clarifications in the writing, but it is getting close to being ready. The main idea is strong, but assumptions are made regarding some main ideas that need to be addressed. Just the syntax, grammar, and writing clarifications need to be worked on. Then I think this paper is almost ready.

Suggestions for improving and polishing the rough draft:

Page. 1.

In the list of authors' names after the title, the group title "Mapped the Closest Address" is likely a mistake. The people created the article, not the performing group.

P.2.

Small detail: I see in the abstract that MaCA (which is a group of people but is also a singular entity) is then described as "their." Consider whether the MaCA should be listed as singular or plural. It seems like a group (singular) when you speak about it as a whole. The grammar was a bit confusing due to word choice.

The word "this" is a dangling modifier and should be followed by another word. "This ___process/practice/investigation? ___ includes..."

I see you stated, "The article discusses." An article is not a living being and cannot discuss anything. I urge you to instead state something like this, "The authors discuss..."

P.3. Introduction:

Question: Is the cat a non-human person? You don't suggest it as such, but maybe you will later.

Again, I see you stated, "The article draws." An article is not a living being and cannot draw anything. I urge you to instead state something like this, "The authors draw..."

The syntax is not working in this sentence. "Furthermore, the choreography values "a (utopian) idea of a blurring of the distinction between (the value of) human and non-human creatures appears." (Buh, 2022, 48). Remove the word "appears."

I imagine you will go on to explain what "*malfunction and disobedient movement*" are; however, I am desiring an explanation here when you first introduce it.

Footnote 1: Dangling modifier again. See "This is...." What is "this?"

p.4.

I noticed you use the first names of the contributors rather than the surnames: Maharu, Shuntaro, Catalina, and Alex. This choice may be a way to make the article seem personable; however, typically contributors are addressed in articles by their surnames. *Yoshida, Arturo, Fernandez, and Maeno.*

"Catalina's mother" should probably be changed to "Fernandez' mother."

p.5.

Which "province" did you travel to? I think you might need to state it. You called it "the province." You mentioned, "*our mountain portraits*" but we don't know what those are. Can you explain? Does the phrase "*non-human choreographies*" imply that the kudzu is creating itself? What is the role of the human in this choreography?

p.6.

Are the "*tips*" the root tips or the leaf tips?

The word *very* is discouraged in English. The use of the word *vigorously* alone is more powerful. *very vigorously*

If you "*we unravel the composition of kudzu.*" Isn't this a modernist approach to affecting nature? Maybe you need to describe that the kudzu guided your movement, and it was the choreographer.

Party of this sentence is sounding vague. Can you clarify? Why is "the acceptance of the mountains" followed by the words, "the Earth beings?" I am not sure what you are implying there. Can you explain a bit more?

What are "*multispecies stories*?" You don't explain this concept and it will be unknown to readers. What is a "*Shugendo practitioner*?" Be sure to describe so readers don't have to Google it to understand this.

I think this sentence should start your paragraph, not end it:

"The mountains transmitted knowledge to us, and we were tuning in to their rhythms rather than the other way around."

What does the phrase, "*encountered a composition of kudzu*" mean? Did the composition/design emerge from your efforts, or did you encounter it as you walked through the woods? The word "encounter" is more often about a happenstance meeting with something along a path. I think your use is different, so maybe find a different word.

What type of dance scores are you referring to in this passage? "When we translate the kudzu movement into dance scores." Can you clarify the type of dance score? There are so many in existence. Is it written on paper?

Is "*the witness of kudzu*" any person who happens to be watching the activity?

In the section titled, Navigation of the living archives and ecological considerations: Clumsy-Seeming Mountains, the installation (Tokamachi Snow Center), I think you are likely introducing a new installation, yet you simply state "Our installation was housed..." I think you need to signal to readers that you are dealing with a different installation. Such as: "In the Clumsy-Seeming Mountains installation, ..."

p.7

I strongly think that this paragraph is extremely important to your paper and should be included as regular text, not as a footnote. It seems to ground so much of what I keep asking about right here in this paragraph. I would move it up into the paper somewhere. It is a strong paragraph: "we theorize an other-than-human choreography that relativizes the non-human's non-danceable movement and more-than-human's non-moving movement. based on Western notions. A key point is the cross-cultural approach that avoids a singular Western notion and offers the clumsy-seemingness which deconstructs a central point of view and proposes more symbiotic and altruistic worldviews and approaches."

I think you can remove these couple of words from the photo caption Figure 10: "*Figure 11 has been*" and start with "Reproduced with permission..."

"composed by Catalina" should probably be changed to "*composed by Fernandez.*"

I think readers will not know what you mean by "slightly 'off'" Can you give a more tangible experiential descriptor or adjective?

p.8

What sort of dance scores are you referring to on page 8?

What do you mean by archives? You must tell us what that is. It sounds interesting, but you've not told us.

You wrote "*By placing MaCA's archives.*" Typically, in English we would say "*By placing MaCA's archives ____ (next to, near, beside, above, juxtaposed with, etc), we aimed to...*" I think you need to qualify what you are doing by adding the right word there.

I noticed you switch from present to past to present tense in this paragraph. Maybe stay with present tense and speak about it as if it is happening. It will allow readers to experience it as if it is happening for them. I edited these words in your paragraph below: hanging, guide, are, so, can, meanwhile.

Even though rice fields have been heavily domesticated, they continue to exhibit behaviors that are not solely driven by human desires; rather, they also demonstrate their own performances. Indeed, visitors are aware of the performance of rice fields and watch three huge mountain objects, each about three to five meters in diameter, made by collecting and weaving local kudzu, **hanging** in the space. Mountains made of kudzu in the building and the real mountains outside **guide** the visitors to in-between perspectives. Mountains **are** vessels of organisms and living archives **so** that visitors **can** walk around inside/outside of mountains, **meanwhile** staying close to Earth beings. Thus, the choreography of the clumsy-seeming mountains reopens the discussion of ecological considerations and brings a sense of kinship.

I think the insertion of the paragraph about the search for second-hand materials and plastic seems oddly placed or even unnecessary. Was this factor a part of your mission or something you simply experienced? If you don't mention it earlier as part of the project, it comes up as odd on page 8. We are already into your philosophy and mission, and this seems to appear out of nowhere. Do you need it? Maybe earlier you could briefly mention in a method-section about how you managed to use 90% found natural objects in your performance and only the sound and lighting equipment introduced manufactured plastic goods.

Footnote 14: Does Japan have the "best functioning e-waste management System" in the world? I think you left out a modifier.

Where you wrote "*he describes*" I think you need to say who said that. There are too many names in the paragraph. I think it's Yoshida, but it's hard to follow and I had to check the footnote to be sure.

p.9

Be sure to call Maša only by the surname Buh. First names are never used when speaking respectfully in academic writing.

Conclusion:

You could say, in this case study, we... I thought it was a case study, but now you call it an essay. This is confusing. Isn't it more of a report about a case study?

I think your paragraph would be stronger if you dropped out the word "*effectively*"

Why qualify your experience when it is more about understanding the process and the relationship?

p.11

Possibly reconsider changing one of the awareness words here: "awareness of environmental awareness..." Maybe instead state the consciousness of environmental awareness. Or maybe you wish to repeat the word for meaning. In that case keep it.

Maybe state which decade you are referring to in "over a decade"?

Before this statement, "At the time of writing," maybe you could put a heading such as

Suggestions for Future Research.

Ethics and consent:

You wrote "Ethical approval and consent were not required." Was this made clear to you through an IRB application. If so, you could say, this study was approved and categorized as exempt upon IRB review.

I think you have an extra word "that" in here:

The authors confirm that consent to publish the name of Luz Marina Giraldo.

Data Availability:

"No data are associated with this article". It should be "data is"

References:

For some reason this item is capitalized differently than your other references. Your other references are lowercase.

Frischkorn M: More-Than-Human Choreography: Handling Things Between Logistics and Entanglement. Bielefeld

Note: I'm not sure it's needed, but you could put the dates when each of the photographs were taken, if they were taken in a particular year or season of a year.

Is the background of the case's history and progression described in sufficient detail?

Partly

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Partly

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Not applicable

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full access and reuse by other researchers?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the data and analysis?

Yes

Is the case presented with sufficient detail to be useful for teaching or other practitioners?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Ph.D. in Dance in Higher Education and Administration Extensive experience publishing qualitative and statistical research about the arts Editor and creator of an online academic, peer-reviewed journal about dance Author of a peer-reviewed book and multiple articles on dance topics Educator of site-specific processes in the arts Experience with dance in South East Asia and Japan.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.
